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Research Article

**DIABETES PREVALENCE IN PATIENTS PRESENTING IN
THE OUTDOOR DEPARTMENT OF MAYO HOSPITAL
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Abstract:

Objective: the main objective of this research was to determine the prevalence of diabetes in patients presenting in the outdoor department of tertiary care hospitals.

Study design: this is a cross-sectional study.

Place and duration of study: This research was conducted from February 2019 to November 2019 in Mayo Hospital Lahore for ten months.

Materials and Methods: This research involved a total of 100 patients of both sexes, aged more than 18 years. To find the random amounts of blood sugar, the Optical Glucometer was used. This research included patients with a history of polyuria, polyphagia, and polydipsia. Pregnant females have been removed from our study. Many of the patients received informed consent. The approval of the Ethical Review Committee was adopted. To gather the data, proforma was built carefully and then analyzed using SPSS V.20.

Results: There were 55 females and 45 males in our sample. The average age was 36. In 81% of patients, diabetes-related symptoms were found, while 19% of patients had no symptoms of diabetes. Among these patients, 85% were found to be diabetic with BSR levels of about 126 mg/dl, while 15% were non-diabetic with BSR levels of about 126 mg/dl. In these patients, 145.97 ± 22.02 mg/dl was the mean BSR seen. It was 142.89 ± 16.95 mg/dl for female patients, while it was 152.85 ± 23.94 mg/dl for male patients. Of the patients, 25% had a good family history.

Conclusion: Our research concluded that there is a high prevalence of people with diabetes among outdoor patients.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is widely characterized as elevated blood sugar levels for an extended period. Diabetes patients may either have no symptoms or may have polyuria, polydipsia, and polyphagia. There are four primary types of type-I and type-II diabetes, while two other factors include gestational and diabetes. Many individuals are diagnosed while doing other regular tests. The prevention of acute and chronic complications includes early diagnosis and strict supervision. In some instances, diabetic ketoacidosis, hyperosmolar nonketotic coma, hypoglycemia, or even coma may be acute complications. Chronic renal disease, stroke, diabetic foot and ulcers, diabetic retinopathy, and cardiovascular diseases can be long-term complications. In developing countries, according to the WHO, the incidence of diabetes will rise by up to 170 per cent by 2025. For this disease, early diagnosis and prompt treatment are therefore needed. The main objective of this research was to determine the prevalence of diabetes in patients presenting in the outdoor tertiary care hospital department. This will aid in early disease identification and control, which will eliminate complications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This research involved a total of 100 patients of both sexes, aged more than 18 years. To find the random amounts of blood sugar, the Optical Glucometer was used. This research included patients with a history of polyuria, polyphagia, and polydipsia. Pregnant females have been removed from our study. Many of the patients received informed consent. The approval of the Ethical Review Committee was adopted. To gather the data, proforma is built carefully and then analyzed using SPSS V.20.

RESULTS:

There were 45 males and 55 females in our study. The median age was 36. In 81 per cent of patients, diabetes-related symptoms were seen, while 19 per cent of patients had no symptoms of diabetes. 85% of these patients were found to be diabetic with BSR levels of 126mg/dl, while 15% were non-diabetic with BSR levels of 126mg/dl. The mean BSR seen in these patients was 145.97 ± 22.02 mg/dl. It was 142.89 ± 16.95 mg/dl among female patients, while it was 152.85 ± 23.94 mg/dl among male patients. Of the patients, 25 per cent had a good family history.

DISCUSSION:

In patients presenting in outdoor departments of tertiary care hospitals, high DM prevalence is seen. The main factor for this high prevalence may be that

this research included patients with symptoms of diabetes. On the other hand, 19 patients with no symptoms were included, but according to our report, 15 patients were non-diabetic. This indicates that even in the absence of symptoms, diabetes can still be present. According to some studies in Pakistan, the exact reason behind this increased prevalence is not yet apparent, but the contributing factors may be increased industrialization, urbanization, and eating habits. There are more significant risks of complications such as macro and microvascular, leading to a destructive lifestyle. Some studies also indicate that along with exercise and physical activity, improving eating patterns can reduce the risk of complications that keep diabetes under control.

CONCLUSION:

Our study concluded that the incidence of people with diabetes among outdoor patients is high. To avoid serious complications linked to this, early management and treatment are necessary. Modification of lifestyle may decrease the risk of complications.

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